

PARVİZ FİRUDİNOĞLU KAZİMİ

Baku State University, Associate Professor, Doctor of Philosophy.

ORCID: - [0000-0001-5577-4773]

GULNARE YUSİFQİZİ YUSİFOVA

Baku State University, Associate Professor, Doctor of Philosophy,

ORCID: - [0000-0003-0822-0254]

SAMIRA ISGANDAR MAMMADOVA

Sumgayit State University, Associate Professor, Doctor of Philosophy.

ORCID: - [0000-0003-0675-9248]

**SOCIAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL ESSENCE OF THE PROBLEM OF SATISFACTION OF READER
CONSUMPTION****Abstract:**

The rapid growth of information volume and the diversity of channels for obtaining it confront the satisfaction of the reader-consumer with a number of parallel interests. Identifying the socio-philosophical nature of reader satisfaction in the triangle of object, subject and process can play an important role in understanding the chaos that exists in the information environment.

In addition to considering the problem as a component of social processes, it is important to evaluate it against the backdrop of the influence of new ICT technologies on our daily lives and the transformation of the cultural environment.

Reader satisfaction can be achieved through concepts that meet the information needs of consumers, fulfil the demands of cultural society and respond to national, regional and global challenges.

The idea of explaining reader satisfaction from the point of view of commercial interests and the commercialization of the process does not reveal the true nature of the problem, and the directions for solving the problem in service to the civilizational process remain unanswered.

Libraries, whether traditional, digital or hybrid models, represent a valuable information heritage of human society. Their sustainability and ability to maintain their position in the modern information age largely depend on the correct assessment of their socio-philosophical essence.

This article attempts to analyze the scientific, theoretical and empirical aspects of the problem and determine its connection with existing theories. The problem of consumer evaluation of reader

satisfaction, its commercial approach, its social value, cultural studies, secularity is expressed in its socio-philosophical essence.

The article examines the long-term social consequences of the deliberate introduction of false information services and disinformation into the process of providing information, and also reveals their socio-philosophical essence.

Keywords: *reader satisfaction, socio-philosophical essence, information service, information literacy, information reliability.*

Introduction.

Information has become the driving force of the 21st century economy, and intellectual capital is becoming increasingly valuable and is an indispensable factor of production. Prompt access to accurate and complete information is today the most important social need of society and one of the main tasks of information support institutions, primarily libraries. Today, in addition to libraries, there are many organizations, including commercial enterprises, providing information services. Access to new information as a result of constant knowledge updating is considered the most important element of competitiveness in the field of information services.¹

QUALITY INDICATOR OF READERS' SATISFACTION

In the process of providing information to a modern person, the main indicators are considered to be efficiency, continuity of service, effectiveness and quality. Unlike commercial information institutions, the main goal of information services in government agencies and library and information institutions is not financial gain, but meeting the needs of readers. Ensuring reader satisfaction is a key condition for library and information institutions in order to maintain and expand their information market in the global information environment created by ICT. To ensure user satisfaction, it is necessary to determine what the modern reader expects from the enterprise and how he perceives the information service provided, calculate the satisfaction index, and determine the factors influencing the index.² Determining these factors emphasizes the need for scientific analysis using service quality measurement methods.

The quality of information services can be characterized as the result of the user's subjective assessment of the level of services provided to him and a comparison of the level of services provided to him with the level that he, in his opinion, deserves.

¹ Kazimi, P. F. O., Oqlu, I. I. A., & Qizi, Y. G. Y. (2022). Philosophical view on information theory (The path from the divine to the digital world). *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 32, 724.

² Kazimi, P. F. (2021). Conflict of relevance and reliability of information and the global network. *Trends in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(1), 1-2.

When speaking about the quality of information services, various forms of interaction between the enterprise and users are considered. They are defined as communication channels in the enterprise building, the quality of web services and other possibilities. In some cases, when visiting libraries or visiting websites, readers and users may encounter a shortage of library information resources, a lack of services in narrow areas, low employee efficiency and poor service, slowness and incorrectness of responses, inability to respond to a request or receiving irrelevant, inaccurate information.

Thus, the "human factor" comes to the fore. That is, a library and information specialist who has the combined potential of professional knowledge, skills and abilities, is motivated to work, shows dedication to his professional activities, has personal qualities that help attract users, can ensure an increase in the level of service. The level of competence of a librarian-bibliographer is determined by erudition, experience, mindset and moral and psychological qualities. Attentiveness, goodwill, politeness, patience and accuracy, competence, attention to the needs of a specific user - these are the main signs of high-quality library service, which should form the basis of the organizational culture of the library.

Sources

In the librarianship of the USSR, the assessment of library and information activities was determined mainly by the archive data of libraries - funds, rare copies, prepared bibliographic indexes and materials, conducted bibliographic reviews, the number of readers, library attendance, etc. indicators. Unfortunately, this methodology is still used in Azerbaijan. However, to assess the quality of library and information activities in developed countries such as Western Europe, Turkey, the USA, Canada, etc., a different approach has been used since the 1990s, and in the Russian Federation, a different approach has recently been used - methods for measuring the quality of service. It should be noted that problem-oriented issues related to the quality of library services have been studied in the areas of library management and marketing, quality management, and personnel management, the authors A. Parazurman, L. Berry and B. Zaitmal, K. Cook, F. Heath, B. Thompson and others in their works demonstrated methods for measuring service quality.³

CONSEQUENCES OF DISINFORMATION

An information consumer can be satisfied with a false information service. If an information consumer actively uses false or unreliable sources, they may face serious socio-cultural crises that affect both the individual and society as a whole. This may be due to the spread of disinformation and false information, as well as the presentation of false information as truthful. The number of myths, misconceptions and misconceptions about reality is growing in society. As a result, trust in official institutions is lost. People stop trusting science, education, the media and government

³ Stebbins, R. A. (2012). *The committed reader: Reading for utility, pleasure, and fulfillment in the twenty-first century*. Scarecrow Press.

agencies. The “post-truth” effect occurs when personal emotions become more important than real facts. Society becomes radical and polarized, false sources often encourage extremist ideas and radical actions, and society becomes increasingly fragmented along political, religious, ethnic or ideological lines. In this process, critical thinking is reduced. The constant consumption of unreliable information destroys the skills of analysis, fact-checking and argumentation. People are becoming increasingly susceptible to manipulation, rumors, and propaganda.

The victim of systematic disinformation faces a distortion of cultural memory and identity. Historical facts are replaced by myths, ideas about one's roots, traditions, and national values are distorted.⁴ Similarly, social and political crises arise, and false information can be used to create provocations, create tensions between different groups in society, which leads to increased conflicts, instability, and even social unrest. Therefore, the use of unreliable sources destroys the foundations of a rational society, harms education, culture, trust, and stability. That is why in the modern world, information literacy is as important as basic education and upbringing.

The long-term detrimental effects of poor information services in education, library and information services can be extremely serious and manifest themselves at various levels - personal, institutional and social. The formation of distorted knowledge in the educational process, the receipt of inaccurate, incomplete or outdated information by students and learners leads to the formation of erroneous ideas about the scientific picture of the world, weak specialists are formed who are unable to solve complex problems or use the scientific method, the general level of education decreases, simplified or distorted education weakens the national education system. As a result, there is a shortage of qualified personnel and the absence of world standards.

There is a weakening of research capacity. Misinformation prevents students and young scientists from conducting quality research and relying on reliable sources, which leads to stagnation of science and technology and a lack of innovation.

In the field of library and information services, there is a decline in the reputation of libraries. If a library provides unreliable sources or fails to direct users to quality information, it loses its reputation as a reliable conductor of knowledge, leading to a decline in audiences and a crisis of libraries as institutions of public trust.⁵

The role of libraries as cultural and educational centers is being destroyed. Libraries are traditionally institutions that support education, democracy, and a culture of critical thinking. Disinformation is

⁴ Bayramzadeh, S. Z. O., & Kazimi, P. F. O. (2020). Ethnogenesis of Minor Peoples or the Search For Eternal History (Source Study of Problem). *American Scientific Journal*, (42-2), 4-10.

⁵ Kazimi, P. F. O. (2025). Dynamics of Science Development in Azerbaijan 2023-2024 (Primary Scientometric Analysis). *Journal of Management World*, 2025(1), 255-257.

destroying this educational mission, leading to increased ignorance, library closures, and the decline of cultural infrastructure.

If the problem of incorrect information services is not resolved, then in 10–20 years this may lead to a systemic decline in the level of education, culture, and science, or even to a decline and complete loss of national competitiveness on a global scale.

Falsification of history in education, especially if it is carried out on a massive and targeted scale, in the long term leads to the marginalization of society, its fragmentation, and isolation from real history and development. Distortion of history through false textbooks and “pseudo-heroes” does not lead to true patriotic education, but to isolationism, fanaticism, stagnation, and long-term degradation. Intensive teaching of myths and falsified history has a long-term negative impact on the development of society. In the 19th-20th centuries, legends about the "great and ancient Armenian kingdom", "pioneers of world civilization", "eternal struggle for independence" were actively created among the Armenian intelligentsia, especially in emigration, which were significantly embellished in comparison with real historical sources.

Textbooks, literature and popular culture educate schoolchildren on the images of heroes and the "eternal people" to whom "everyone is indebted", while simultaneously distorting and contrasting real historical interactions with neighboring peoples.⁶ This forms a complex of vindictiveness and exclusivity in the national consciousness, which ultimately leads to the extreme politicization of historical memory, difficulty in integrating into a multipolar world, and the creation of an environment of constant existence in a state of conflict.

Ideologization of history turns historical plots into the creation of an almost religious "cult", isolationism, a sense of "specialness" hinders normal integration into the world. Young people facing an identity crisis are experiencing a deep cultural crisis. Historical truth does not humiliate people – it gives them the opportunity to consciously build their future. However, living in fictional myths dooms a person to constant crises and defeats.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS:

The problem of reader satisfaction is an important aspect not only of the science studying library and information activities, but also of the broader social and philosophical sphere. It also covers such categories as knowledge, needs, interests, perceptions and value orientations of society.

The social essence of reader satisfaction, in the context of reader-user satisfaction, is determined mainly by the degree of compliance of information resources and services provided with user requests. In the social sphere, this means ensuring the availability of information, books, digital resources, scientific publications and other materials necessary for self-development and

⁶ Stowe, W. W. (1982). Satisfying Readers: A Review-Essay. *Texas Studies in Literature and Language*, 24(1), 102–119. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40754674>

professional growth. Creating equal access to information for all groups of the population, regardless of social status, age and place of residence, expresses the principle of social justice. Cultural and cognitive expectations are also taken into account, which guarantees that the content of literature corresponds to the needs and worldview of the reader.

From a philosophical point of view, reader satisfaction can depend on a number of factors. For example.⁷The epistemological aspect - satisfaction is expressed as a reflection of the cognitive needs of the individual. Every person has a thirst for knowledge, and his level of satisfaction depends on the extent to which the information provided helps him to expand his understanding of the world.

Ethical and existential aspects are also taken into account. Reading is especially important in literary and philosophical works as a way of understanding oneself and the world around us, and finding the meaning of life. Information complies with moral and ethical standards and ideas of society, and ensures the reader's participation in the process of forming his or her worldview and critical thinking.

The quality of information services, the efficiency of libraries, and the availability of digital archives play an important role as factors influencing reader satisfaction. When personalizing recommendations, it is important to take into account the interests and preferences of readers when choosing literature. This process requires an individual approach, and the organization of the service should be based on important methodological guidelines.

The reliability of the selected and provided sources is an important factor for reader satisfaction, since the sources must inspire confidence in the reader, and readers must be confident that the information is reliable and based on scientific data.

One of the factors that characterizes our modern era is taking into account the constantly changing needs of readers and consumers. When providing services, it is necessary to take into account the dynamics of this process, ensure the impact of digitalization and the development of multimedia content. Reader satisfaction is not only a subjective feeling of comfort from the information received, but also a complex phenomenon that includes social, philosophical and cognitive processes. To achieve it, it is necessary to integrate new technologies, develop library and information services, and take into account the individual needs of society.⁸

THE "READER" MODEL

The concept of "reader" sounds differently in many languages and performs different functions. The concept of "reader" in Azerbaijani is described in detail by the honored scientist, honorary professor of Baku State University Abuzer Khalafov in his book "Introduction to Library Science" in the text

⁷ Yusifova, G. Y., & Kazimi, P. F. (2025). Logical social similarities and imitation (Phenomenon influencing human thinking). *Edelweiss Applied Science and Technology*, 9(4), 2189-2195.

⁸ Kazimi, P. F. O. (2021). Democratic countries and ways of influencing the nature of information. *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 22, 847.

entitled "Structural characteristics and main elements of the library", where the term "reader" is widely explained with the help of scientific concepts and is considered as the main element of the library. "The word "reader" itself carries an intellectual quality. When we say "reader", we mean an intelligent person in library and information activities, a person who loves books and knows how to evaluate them. If we consider this as a classical model, then we need to distinguish the reader from the modern consumer of information. Not every user, not every consumer can rise to the level of a reader, and specialists working in this field fully understand how right the scientist is in expressing his views. The word "reader" in its content does not mean a person who has a daily need for a book, but rather, the title of reader can have intellectuals who have a constant need for books, who constantly improve their personal and professional level, spiritual wealth, who constantly participate in the public activities of the library, who strive for systematic acquisition of knowledge, creating a library environment.⁹ It is enough to note the idea that the "true reader" is noted.

The existence of libraries without readers speaks of the tragedy of every nation. We, as a society, must work systematically and purposefully to overcome this tragedy. Here, the first task of parents is to encourage their children to read books as part of the initial pedagogical process, then teachers should join this work, recommending various books for students to read in addition to lessons and requiring them to read this literature during summer vacations.

Reader satisfaction is influenced by many factors, and a separate study should be conducted on this issue. The library environment is of particular importance for reader satisfaction. Readers spend 7-8 hours in the library, and in some cases even more, reading. At the same time, ergonomic conditions must be created to ensure the reader's comfort. An ergonomic environment directly or indirectly affects the human body, the elements that make up the musculoskeletal system, bones, joints, muscles and the nervous system. An ergonomic environment is also important for employees in terms of occupational health and safety. If this is not achieved, the librarian's dissatisfaction will manifest itself in the service process, and will also cause justified dissatisfaction among readers. When assessing reader satisfaction in various library networks, the goals and objectives set by the reader are taken into account, and only then an objective picture is formed.

Conclusion.

As can be seen, user satisfaction implies an assessment of the importance of organizational culture for improving the quality of library services. Because it is based on a positive image of the library, which contributes to the formation of an impeccable reputation and the dissemination of ideas about high quality of service. Libraries, whether traditional, digital or hybrid models, are a valuable information heritage of human society. Studying and evaluating the work of library professionals involved in service processes allows us to identify both the capabilities of library staff and the

⁹ Kazimi, P. F. O., & Guliyeva, N. A. G. (2023). " Time" spent in youth's "global information space"(problems of satisfaction of reading or information need). *Procedia Computer Science*, 219, 720-723.

strengths and weaknesses of human resource management. In this regard, the importance of the following personnel issues is taken into account. The effectiveness of the librarian, the level of dedication of employees to their profession, a high culture of service, labor and professional discipline (timely and accurate performance of job responsibilities), competent and high-quality performance of work, management discipline (timely and accurate performance of tasks), the quality of management and control over the work process should be monitored in a timely manner.

The use of modern information and communication technologies and the "increasing spread of this process" are increasingly pushing people to remote access to information. Most readers who receive comprehensive library and information services from libraries are serious researchers, scientists and industry specialists. Since these reader groups have a special influence on the economic, social and cultural life of society, it is important that libraries can respond to complex requests of different levels, provide a high level of service and satisfy readers.

Obviously, ensuring high satisfaction of readers (consumers) requires significant financial support. Although universities provide this provision at the expense of their own budgets, public libraries, especially children's libraries, are provided for by the state and the budget. Therefore, it is important to determine reader satisfaction in accordance with the categories of library structures and model it differently in accordance with their goals and objectives.

In the field of formation of the information environment, the ways of obtaining, disseminating and using information by people are changing, which seriously affects the development and culture of society. Therefore, in order for this process to be successful, it is useful to consider and coordinate different areas such as technology, content, communication and education.

REFERENCES

- Stebbins, R. A. (2012). *The committed reader: Reading for utility, pleasure, and fulfillment in the twenty-first century*. Scarecrow Press.
- Stowe, W. W. (1982). Satisfying Readers: A Review-Essay. *Texas Studies in Literature and Language*, 24(1), 102–119. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40754674>
- Yusifova, G. Y., & Kazimi, P. F. (2025). Logical social similarities and imitation (Phenomenon influencing human thinking). *Edelweiss Applied Science and Technology*, 9(4), 2189-2195.
- Kazimi, P. F. O. (2025). Dynamics of Science Development in Azerbaijan 2023-2024 (Primary Scientometric Analysis). *Journal of Management World*, 2025(1), 255-257.
- Kazimi, P. F. O., Oqlu, I. I. A., & Qizi, Y. G. Y. (2022). Philosophical view on information theory (The path from the divine to the digital world). *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 32, 724.
- Bayramzadeh, S. Z. O., & Kazimi, P. F. O. (2020). Ethnogenesis of Minor Peoples or the Search For Eternal History (Source Study of Problem). *American Scientific Journal*, (42-2), 4-10.

Kazimi, P. F. (2021). Conflict of relevance and reliability of information and the global network. *Trends in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(1), 1-2.

Kazimi, P. F. O. (2021). Democratic countries and ways of influencing the nature of information. *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 22, 847.

Kazimi, P. F. O., & Guliyeva, N. A. G. (2023). " Time" spent in youth's "global information space"(problems of satisfaction of reading or information need). *Procedia Computer Science*, 219, 720-723.